

^{13}C NMR Chemical Shifts of some 1,4-Disubstituted-benzenes and Substituent Chemical Shifts for some Substituents

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The ^{13}C nmr chemical shifts for a large number of monosubstituted benzenes have been used to derive the substituent effects on ^{13}C nmr chemical shifts of C-1, C-2, C-3 and C-4 of benzene

moiety¹. We have chosen some 1,4-disubstituted aromatic compounds for discovering the additivity of the substituent effects on chemical shifts. In these compounds, the substituents are expected to affect the chemical shifts through the electronic effect only.

Results and Discussion

The observed ^{13}C nmr chemical shifts of some 1,4-disubstituted-benzenes (1-8) are summarised in Table 1. The chemical shifts for all carbons were assigned based upon DEPT experiments.

The substituent effects on ^{13}C nmr chemical shifts of monosubstituted benzene carbons are well documented^{1,2}. It has been also concluded that the chemical shifts for multisubstituted aromatics are predictable based upon the additive nature of these substituent effects¹. However, in multisubstituted nonaromatic systems, the deviation from the simple additivity of the chemical shift effects has been observed if the substituents could interact electronically as well as sterically³. Such electronic and steric interactions are expected to have even stronger effects on simple additivity of chemical shifts of carbons of multisubstituted aromatics. The characteristics of the additive nature of the substituent effects on ^{13}C nmr chemical shifts of 1,4-disubstituted-benzenes may be shown by equation (1),

$$\delta_{\text{ci}}^{\text{obs}} = 128.5 + \Delta\delta_{\text{ci}}^{\text{x}} + \Delta\delta_{\text{ci}}^{\text{y}} \quad (1)$$

($i = 1, 2, 3$ and 4)

TABLE 1-¹³C NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS IN SOME 1,4-DISUBSTITUTED-BENZENES (1-8)

Carbon	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
C-1	112.50	112.39	131.90	131.89	131.83	158.67	159.14	158.95
C-2	132.10	132.14	129.43	129.44	129.81	114.15	114.18	114.17
C-3	116.16	117.56	114.40	115.87	113.68	127.73	128.71	128.70
C-4	157.96	156.90	157.29	156.21	158.00	133.48	133.79	133.61
C-5	116.16	117.56	114.40	115.87	113.68	127.73	128.71	128.70
C-6	132.10	132.14	129.43	129.44	129.81	114.15	114.18	114.17
C-7	63.56	70.06	63.35	69.80	55.20	55.34	55.33	55.31
C-8	14.66	21.62	14.84	22.04	43.75	55.34		44.23
C-9		21.62	39.32	22.04	145.54			145.10
C-10			137.88	39.34	111.54			111.94
C-11			115.33	137.86	21.98			22.08
C-12				115.32				
C-1'						158.67	126.66	138.20
C-2'						114.15	128.16	129.25
C-3'						127.73	126.75	126.70
C-4'						133.48	140.64	138.60
C-5'						127.73	126.75	126.70
C-6'						114.15	126.18	129.25

where $\delta_{C_i}^{obs}$ is the observed chemical shift of *i*-th carbon, 128.5 is the chemical shift (in ppm) of nonsubstituted benzene carbon, and $\Delta\delta_{C_i}^X$ and $\Delta\delta_{C_i}^Y$ are the substituent effects (i.e. substituent chemical shifts in ppm) on *i*-th carbon of substituent

X and Y respectively. In the calculation of unknown substituent chemical shifts, one of the substituents is considered as reference substituent. The calculated values of substituent chemical shifts in terms of chemical shifts for a few

TABLE 2-¹³C SUBSTITUENT CHEMICAL SHIFTS ($\Delta\delta_c$) OF 1,4-DISUBSTITUTED-BENZENES

Substituent	Reference substituent	C-1	C-2	C-3	C-4
OCH ₂ CH ₃ H	Br	31.1	-13.0	0.2	-10.5
OC-CH ₃ CH ₃	Br	30.0	-12.6	0.2	-10.6
CH ₂ C=CH ₂ CH ₃	OCH ₃	11.0	0.3	-0.4	-1.9
CH ₂ CH=CH ₂ H	OCH ₂ CH ₃	7.1	-1.1	-1.1	-2.3
	OC-CH ₃ CH ₃	7.1	-1.1	0.0	-2.3
C ₆ H ₅	OCH ₃	13.0 (13.1)	-0.8 (-1.1)	0.1 (0.4)	-0.8 (-1.2)
4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	H	12.1	-1.7	-0.3	-1.8
	OCH ₃	12.7	-1.8	-0.1	-1.2
	CH ₂ C=CH ₂ CH ₃	12.0	-1.4	0.5	-1.3
4-CH ₂ =CCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	OCH ₃	12.8	-0.8	-1.1	-0.9

* Values in parenthesis are derived from monosubstituted benzenes (Ref 1).

substituents are shown in Table 2. The validity of this approach is evident from almost similar substituent chemical shifts obtained for 4-MeOC₆H₄ using three different reference substituents (Table 2) and the substituent chemical shifts for C₆H₅ is similar to the reported values derived from monosubstituted benzene.

Experimental

¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Bruker AM 300 spectrometer (75.46 MHz) using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal reference.

All the compounds (1-8) were prepared in our laboratory. Their methods of preparation and other physical data are reported elsewhere⁴.

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